

Inter-Laboratory Comparison of Reference Systems for DC Power Quality Measurements

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Abstract—Low-voltage DC microgrids are a popular solution for a direct integration of more and more renewable energy sources. In this scenario, it is reasonable to expect that the power signal will not consist of pure DC components but will be affected by disturbances and power quality (PQ) events coming from the AC bulk grid as well as from switching power supplies or time-varying loads. To the state of the art, the normative framework does not provide a rigorous approach towards DCPQ analysis. We lack a clear and unambiguous definition of some quantities (e.g., DC power) or measurement methods (e.g., DC ripple). In order to solve this problem, the recent project *DC grids* has developed two reference systems for DCPQ at METAS and VSL laboratories. In this paper, we compare the systems' performance by means of a measurement campaign on the same transfer standard. The results confirm the consistency of the two reference systems and provide some insightful inputs for the standardization of these tests in the normative framework.

Index Terms—Low Voltage DC Microgrids, DC Power Quality, DC Power, DC Ripple, Transfer Standard, Inter-Laboratory Comparison.

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern power systems are experiencing a rapid transformation due to the ever-increasing penetration of renewable energy sources (RES) and distributed generation [1]. Most of these resources are characterized by DC outputs, and dedicated power converter are needed to interconnect them to the AC bulk grid [2]. Such a paradigm allows for a drastic reduction of the power system carbon footprint, but is also the root cause for many operational challenges as the loss of rotational inertia and the degradation of power quality [3], [4].

These considerations have boosted the proliferation of low-voltage DC microgrids, where energy production and consumption do not need any intermediate transformation stage. This is particularly beneficial when the energy demand profile can be predicted with sufficient accuracy in advance [5]. Unfortunately, though, the normative framework for DC metering is still intended for traditional DC sources and not consider the

possible uncertainty contributions related to the peculiar RES functioning and the disturbances that may be injected at the point of interconnection with the AC grid. Furthermore, these PQ disturbances are still ill-defined for DC grids [6], [7] and regulation setting proper DCPQ limits is missing completely due to lack of knowledge and practical experience.

The recent project *DC grids* ("Standardisation of measurements for DC electricity grids") [8] aimed at filling this gap by studying the possible consequences of power quality (PQ) events on the measurement infrastructure of low-voltage DC grids. This involves not only the DCPQ meters, but also the DC power and energy meter whose results could be affected by various PQ phenomena (e.g., AC component injections).

First, the project identified the most relevant PQ events in low-voltage DC microgrids. Then, it was necessary to develop reference systems capable of reproducing these operating conditions and providing sufficiently accurate reference values.

At this stage of the research activity, we focus mainly on the effect of AC sinusoidal components on the measurement of DC power and on the measurement of ripple magnitude. Both these quantities have several definitions available in the literature [6], [9]. A clear example in this sense is represented by the DC power definition. In the IEC-62052-11:2021 [10], it is defined as the product of DC voltage and current, in turn defined as average values. However, the standard does not specify neither the sampling rate nor the duration of the averaging interval. For instance, in this regard, the EN 50470-4:2023 [11] states that frequencies up to 10 Hz shall be considered as part of the measurement signal and the averaging interval shall be long enough to minimize the effect of AC power components. In the absence of a clear discrimination between the DC and AC domains, it is reasonable to expect that different instruments may produce different measurement results [12].

In this paper, we present the realization of two reference systems for DCPQ, as developed at METAS and VSL. The comparison between the two setups has been carried out by means of a transfer standard capable of measuring both DC power and DCPQ parameters (e.g., ripple magnitude for both voltage and current signals). The obtained results prove the

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remarkable accuracy and consistency of the two reference system and provide a benchmark for the implementation of metrological services in the field of distorted DC signals.

II. REFERENCE SYSTEMS

In this Section, we present the DCPQ reference systems as developed in the METAS and VSL laboratories. In the following paragraphs, we introduce the hardware architecture of the reference systems, and we briefly describe the processing routine employed for definition of the reference values.

a) *METAS*: Fig. 1 presents the block diagram of the METAS reference system for DCPQ measurements. The setup consists of two independent generation and re-acquisition channels, one for the voltage and one for the current [13].

The device under test (DUT) is presented on the right side as a DC meter. In this context, the setup can be intended for two complementary types of tests. On one side, the assessment of AC component interference in DC power and energy meters. On the other side, the characterization of a DCPQ meter capable of reporting a subset of the traditional PQ parameters (e.g., a spectral analysis of the harmonic range up to 9 kHz). In the first case, the DUT may output the power and energy measurements in different formats: either as an electrical or optical pulse signal whose frequency is scaled to the measured power, or as a digital value stored in the internal registers of the meter. In the second case, the DUT provides different results depending on the selected PQ parameter. For the spectral analysis, the frequency and RMS magnitude of the components are computed over 200 ms gapless intervals. For the PQ events (as voltage dips and swells), the measurement result is based on 10 ms intervals and consists of three indices: timestamp of the event starting point, duration and size of the variation. For the ripple, different definitions can be implemented [14]–[16] as discussed further in the next Section III.

In the METAS setup, a pair of Keysight 33500B function generators are responsible for the generation of the DC and AC component of both voltage and current signals. The two devices are disciplined by the same 10 MHz time base and operate in a master-slave mode (i.e., one triggers the activation of the analog outputs of the other). Such an architecture has a twofold advantage. By sharing the same time base, the two devices can reproduce the exact same AC component frequency on both voltage and current channels. Moreover, the trigger setting allows for reproducing different phase angle offsets between voltage and current channels. This characteristic may result interesting when it is necessary to compensate the group delay of different amplifier stages or when it is necessary to test operating conditions where the AC components produce not only active power, but also reactive power.

In the voltage channel, DC and AC components are first merged by a Krohn-Hite 7620 power amplifier. In this way, it is possible to superpose DC and AC components without introducing significant distortion and keeping the possibility of controlling separately the generation of DC and AC components. The resulting signal is then amplified by means of a Trek PZD 700A DC broadband voltage amplifier to achieve

Fig. 1. Schematic overview of the METAS DCPQ measurement setup.

the voltage levels envisioned by this analysis (i.e., maximum DC voltage of 1 kV).

In the current channel, DC and AC component are generated separately. The DC component is obtained by driving a pair of Delta Elektronika SM 15-400 DC current source operating in parallel (for a total current output of 800 A). Conversely, the AC component is obtained by means of a Clarke-Hess 8100 transconductance amplifier, whose output is limited to 100 A and 100 kHz in terms of magnitude and frequency, respectively. If a larger bandwidth is required, a Guildline 7620 transconductance amplifier allows for reaching the 150 kHz target, at the cost of a lower current magnitude (namely, maximum 8 A). The combination of DC and AC current components is performed by making the two signals pass through a zero-flux DC current transformer with sufficient bandwidth. In this way, the magnetic field produced by both components will be replicated in a single current output (typically, with a transformation ratio in the order of 1:100 or 1:1000). In the METAS setup, this is obtained by means of a Danisense DS600ID with a rated ratio of 1:1500 and a nominal 3 dB bandwidth of 500 kHz.

In its present configuration, the METAS setup allows for generating DC signals corrupted by sinusoidal or triangular ripple, as well as dip and swell phenomena. Further work is on-going in order to implement further functionalities as time varying DC offset profiles (e.g., mimicking the behavior of DC current in EV charging stations [17]).

To define the reference values, the generated signals supplied to the DUT are simultaneously re-acquired by means of a National Instrument (NI) USB-6341 digitizer. The digitizer has a maximum sampling rate of 500 kHz, and the input range can be varied between ± 0.2 V and ± 10 V with a vertical resolution of 16 bit. To transform the voltage and current signals into a range compatible with the digitizer analog front-end, a METAS voltage divider and a DS600ID are employed.

The digitized waveforms are then processed in LabVIEW programming environment. In the case of ripple analysis, the peak-to-peak amplitude as well as the RMS value are extracted. Moreover, a simple spectral analysis based on the Discrete Fourier Transform allows for extracting the most significant spectral components with a resolution of 5 Hz. In the case of dip and swell, instead, a sliding window analysis

Fig. 2. Schematic overview of the VSL DCPQ measurement setup.

allows for identifying the dip and swell level, as percentage of the nominal level of DC voltage and current.

b) VSL: The VSL reference system for DCPQ is presented in Fig. 2. The hardware architecture is derived from an earlier designed testbed for testing AC electricity meters [18] and adapted for use at DC systems [19].

As in the METAS setup, the VSL reference system generates independently the voltages and current signals for the DUT, in this case a DCPQ meter. In parallel, a standard meter developed at VSL allows for defining the reference values for each specific test.

The components for the new setup were selected for the capability of generating wideband signals, ranging from DC up to more than 50 kHz. First, a low-voltage version of the voltage and current signals is generated using an NI PXIe 6733 digital-to-analog converter (DAC). Then, the voltage signal is amplified by a Trek PZD2000A voltage amplifier capable of amplifying signals up to 2 kV, with a rated bandwidth from DC to 150 kHz. In a similar way, the current signal coming from the DAC is amplified by a Clarke-Hess 8100 or an AE Techtron 7728 transconductance amplifier for currents up to 100 A or 16 A, respectively, both capable of amplifying signals from DC up to frequencies well above 100 kHz.

The VSL standard meter employs an NI PXIe 5356 digitizer to measure the generated signals and to define the reference values for both DC voltage and current levels, as well as DCPQ parameters of interest. To measure the generated voltage signals up to 1000 V a resistive/capacitive voltage divider is being built with a ratio of 201:1. The current signal is first transformed by a LEM ITN 900-S ULTRASTAB zero-flux current transformer with a 1:1500 current ratio for frequencies up to several hundreds of kHz to a smaller current signal and with the help of a wideband current shunt transformer to a measurable voltage.

III. INTER-LABORATORY COMPARISON

In this Section, we discuss the methodological aspects and implementation challenges related to the DCPQ inter-laboratory comparison. Furthermore, we sketch a preliminary uncertainty budget, intended to identify the definitional and systematic contributions inherent in DC ripple measurements.

a) Transfer standard: The comparison of such complex reference systems is typically performed by means of transfer standards. First, the reference systems are characterized in METAS and VSL, in terms of stability and accuracy of the generated test signals. Then, by comparing a set of measurements performed on the same transfer standard, we can validate the performance of the different reference systems. In this regard, we consider the measurements of METAS and VSL to be consistent if and only if their expanded uncertainty ranges are (at least, partially) overlapped. Such a decision rule is inspired by the quality management criteria as defined in ISO 9001:2015 [20], and relies on the assumption that the stability of the transfer standard and on the fact that the uncertainty of the reference systems are much lower than the transfer standard one.

For this inter-laboratory comparison, we employ a transfer standard developed in collaboration by METAS and INRIM [21], [22]. The device is capable of measuring DC and active power, but also DCPQ parameters.

The transfer standard relies on an NI CompactDAQ equipped with an acquisition board for the simultaneous acquisition of voltage and current signals. At this stage of the activity, the transfer standard relies on a NI-9205 board, with an input range variable between ± 0.2 V and ± 10 V and a vertical resolution of 16 bit. The transfer standard acquires directly the secondary output of the instrument transformers used also by the reference systems.

The NI-9205 board relies on a Delta-Sigma ADC and - as such - it is not possible to discipline its sampling rate to an external time-base. In principle, this may lead to incoherent sampling conditions, with distortion effects that may depend on the input signal frequency. On the other hand, though, it is worth noticing that the measurand consists only of the DC component. It is thus realistic to assume that any systematic effect can be fully characterized and compensated during the calibration stage.

A LabVIEW software allows to perform the power quality analysis in real-time. In the case of ripple, the RMS amplitude and the frequency are extracted [23]. In the case of dip and swell phenomena, the initial time stamp, the duration and the voltage change are recorded.

b) Test points: For this analysis, we consider a set of test points that are representative of possible distortions in real-world scenarios. In this sense, we consider AC components whose frequency does not exceed a few kHz. Indeed, it is realistic to assume that DC meters and DCPQ meters will apply some sort of low-pass filtering, if not explicitly designed for the supra-harmonic range analysis. In that case, even ACPQ meters employ specific estimation methods that differ from the traditional harmonic analysis [24].

For the sake of clarity, the considered test points are reported in Table I and II. In more detail, Table I presents the parameters for the DC power tests in distorted conditions. At this stage of the research activity, they are considered as influence quantities for the DC power computation and not as possible source of AC active power.

TABLE I
TEST POINTS FOR DC POWER IN DISTORTED CONDITIONS

DC Parameters		Ref. Value DC Power (kW)	AC Parameters		
Voltage (V)	Current (A)		Frequency (Hz)	Voltage (V)	Current (A)
750	500	375	50	75	50
750	500	375	150	75	50
750	500	375	300	75	50
750	500	375	1000	75	50
750	500	375	5000	75	50

TABLE II
VOLTAGE AND CURRENT RIPPLE TEST

DC Parameters		Ripple Parameters		
Voltage (V)	Current (A)	Frequency (Hz)	Voltage (V)	Current (A)
750	500	50	75	-
750	500	150	75	-
750	500	300	75	-
750	500	1000	75	-
750	500	5000	75	-
750	500	50	-	50
750	500	150	-	50
750	500	300	-	50
750	500	1000	-	50
750	500	5000	-	50

In Table II, we report the parameters for the voltage and current ripple tests. For simplicity, we prefer to consider a sinusoidal ripple on a single channel (either voltage or current). Nevertheless, the reference systems can reproduce also other ripple patterns (e.g., multi-tone or triangular) simultaneously on both channels.

As regards ripple measurements, it is important to underline that there exist different feasible definitions of DC ripple, either in the time or in the frequency domain [25]. In the transfer standard and in the VSL reference system, the ripple is derived by the measurement of RMS and DC of the acquired signal. In the METAS reference system, it is computed based on a Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT)-based analysis of the acquired signal. In order to minimize the spectral leakage effect an interpolated DFT estimator has been employed [26].

c) Uncertainty budget: In the following Section, we present the results of the inter-laboratory comparison with respect to the test points in Table I and II. For each test point, we perform ten independent measurements. In each measurement, the transfer standard defines the DC power as the average value of 150 estimates computed over 100 consecutive non-overlapping intervals of 0.2 s (i.e., overall test duration of 30 s). For each measurement, we compute the transfer standard error as the difference between the transfer standard measurement and the reference value.

To compare the results of the two setups, we define the mean error and the corresponding expanded uncertainty both in terms of a percentage of the DC voltage or current. In this regard, we can discriminate between two contributions. On one side, the Type-A variability of the transfer standard

measurement errors. For this analysis, we compute the 95th percentile of the error distribution. On the other side, a preliminary evaluation of the transfer standard Type-B systematic contributions is given in [23]. In this regard, different aspects may be taken into account, from the voltage and current sensors to the software employed for the computation of the DC power. In both METAS and VSL setups, the generation and acquisition channels share the same time-base and therefore the risk for incoherent sampling is nearly negligible for the reference values. The same does not apply for the transfer standard, even if it is reasonable to expect that the main contribution is given by the acquisition board quantization, that results in a worst-case uncertainty of 0.02 %. This result is confirmed by the preliminary results presented in , where the behavior of the transfer standard at different power levels is presented. At 375 kW, the errors due to internal clock and software are in the order of 0.001 % [27]. In a conservative approach, in the following we consider the two contributions statistically independent and we combine their contributions quadratically. However, a more rigorous evaluation of the transfer standard uncertainty is envisioned in order to fully characterize its behavior in distorted conditions.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this Section, we present the experimental results of the inter-laboratory comparison and we discuss their similarity with expected real-world conditions as deduced by some recent measurement campaigns in low voltage DC microgrids.

First, we evaluate the transfer standard measurement of DC power in the presence of AC disturbances. In this context, Fig. 3 presents the statistical distribution of the DC power errors at METAS and VSL in blue and red, respectively. The error is computed comparing the transfer standard estimates against the reference values produced by the METAS and VSL setups. The markers and the vertical bars represent the mean error and the expanded uncertainty associated to each test point.

It is interesting to observe how the measurement results are strongly consistent in both setups. The uncertainty ranges are well overlapped, and the mean errors' difference does not exceed 20 ppm all over the considered frequency range.

In nominal conditions, the DC power error is equal to 0.024 ± 0.007 % and 0.038 ± 0.006 % for METAS and VSL, respectively. The uncertainty bars of these measurements do not overlap, which we attribute to the stability of the transfer standard calibration coefficients during the time between the two measurement campaigns. Given the sensitivity to grounding and impedance mismatches in different measurement chains, it is suggested to repeat the calibration of the transfer standard in each new measurement setup.

Therefore, it is reasonable to say that the addition of the AC spurious components does not affect the transfer standard measurements (at least, for frequencies larger than 10 Hz). On the other hand, we notice a larger uncertainty range: The AC disturbances are not perfectly filtered out by the transfer standard averaging procedure and result in a reduced oscillation of the DC power value. In this regard, it should be

Fig. 3. DC power error distributions as function of the AC component frequency. The markers indicate the mean value, while the vertical bars correspond to the expanded uncertainty.

noted that the transfer standard and the reference system do not share the same time base and thus the assumption that the DC power is computed over an integer number of AC component cycles may not be verified in practice. This assumption is heuristically confirmed by the fact that the uncertainty range decreases as the AC component frequency increases.

In Fig. 4, we present the error distributions for the DC voltage ripple measurements. The results of the two setups are sufficiently consistent with the exceptions of the ripple frequency of 50 and 5000 Hz. In the first case, the METAS setup seems to produce a measurement distribution with opposite polarity with respect to the other test points. A possible reason could be identified in a power supply interference. Similar considerations hold for the VSL error distribution at 5 kHz. This aspect is still currently under investigation, but it is also worth pointing out that the transfer standard acquisition board has not been characterized with such higher distortion and may be particularly sensitive to the impedance coupling with different amplifier and divider circuits.

In a similar way, Fig. 5 presents the error distributions for the DC current measurements. Compared to the voltage case, the mean errors are much more consistent, but the uncertainty ranges are also much larger due to the large Type-A contribution (even higher than $\pm 0.5\%$). The reason for this can be identified in two aspects. On one side, the complex way of superposing DC and AC current components, resulting in higher wideband noise. On the other side, a sensor stage composed by two elements (namely, a zero-flux DCCT and a resistive shunt) that reduces significantly the AC signal magnitude that risks to be submerged among measurement and quantization noise. This phenomenon becomes less evident as the ripple frequency increases. Indeed, it is reasonable to assume that the behaviour of the DCCT may be different depending on the proximity between the AC component and the DC component.

The results presented in this Section proves a general

Fig. 4. Voltage ripple magnitude error distributions as function of the ripple frequency. METAS and VSL results are presented in blue and red, respectively.

Fig. 5. Current ripple magnitude error distributions as function of the ripple frequency. METAS and VSL results are presented in blue and red, respectively.

agreement between METAS and VSL setups. In this sense, it is reasonable to say that both the reference systems are suitable for the characterization of DCPQ meters or DC meters under distorted conditions.

In the ripple measurements, it has been noticed that the expanded uncertainty may rise up to 0.1 % or higher for a nominal ripple magnitude of 10 %. This value gives an idea of what is the expected resolution for DC ripple measurements, and should be taken into account when discussing about the actual bandwidth of DC components.

Recent measurements in low voltage DC microgrids [28]–[32] have shown ripple magnitude levels that are comparable with this uncertainty range. Therefore, it is suggested that modern DCPQ meters will adopt averaging or de-noising techniques capable of improving their resolution also in the presence of time-varying DC offsets [23], [33].

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented the results of an inter-laboratory comparison for DCPQ reference systems. First, the hardware

architecture and the measurement principles of the reference systems were introduced. Then, we presented the procedure for the inter-laboratory comparison with specific focus on the transfer standard and the selected protocol. Finally, we presented the experimental results and we demonstrated the suitability of the two reference systems for two metrological applications that promise to become crucial in modern low voltage DC microgrids, i.e., on the one side, the assessment of spurious injections of AC disturbances in DC power meters, and on the other side, the characterization of DCPQ meters in terms of ripple magnitude measurements.

The proposed results confirm the remarkable accuracy and flexibility of the reference systems. On the other hand, they highlight the space for improvement (particularly for the superposition of DC and AC current components) as well as the still-open issues related to the definition of DC power and DCPQ parameters in distorted conditions.

The next steps of the research activity will focus on the assessment of DC power in the presence of AC active power at different frequencies and on the realization of more realistic distortion conditions as the ones recorded in real-world measurement campaigns.

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